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Impeller Failure in Centrifugal Compressor Caused by Acoustoelastic Resonance

Saeed Hekmat¹, Hamed Navabi², Mostafa Irannejad³, Hamid Shakouri⁴,

Pouya Asgharifard⁵, Akbar Naderpour⁶, Mahdi Arezoomand⁷

Oil Turbo Compressor Equipment Company, Rotor Dynamic Department

Corresponding Author E-mail: navabi@cgc-co.com

Abstract

Over the past five years, repeated failures of the 5th-stage impeller in the CO₂ centrifugal compressor of an Integrally Geared Compressor system at Shiraz Petrochemical Company have been reported. These failures consistently exhibited identical fracture patterns, despite multiple investigations and hypotheses proposed by the rotary equipment department proving inconclusive. This study aimed to uncover the root cause of these recurring failures. Detailed analysis identified acoustoelastic resonance as the likely culprit, resulting from the interaction of closely aligned acoustic and structural natural frequencies with similar mode shapes. This interaction induced high-cycle fatigue, ultimately leading to impeller failure. To address the issue, design modifications were proposed, including scalloping and adjustments to the shroud's thickness profile. The redesigned impeller was subsequently analyzed to achieve a 25% separation margin between acoustic and structural natural frequencies, as recommended in the literature, to mitigate the risk of resonance.

Keywords: Acoustoelastic Resonance, Impeller Failure, Acoustic Eigen Mode Analysis

1 Introduction

The need for high pressure centrifugal compressors in industries such as oil and gas, chemical and petrochemical plants has raised sharply through the recent decades. Since failure of a high-pressure centrifugal compressor can lead to the complete shutdown of a plant, the reliability of such equipment is of primary concern to the owners and runners of mentioned industries. So, it is essential to have extensive knowledge of the failure modes of such compressors. Among various components of a centrifugal compressor, impellers are considered as one of the main elements which transfer mechanical

¹ M.Sc. In Mechanical Engineering, Rotor Dynamics Expert

² PhD. In Mechanical Engineering, Rotor Dynamics Expert

³ PhD. In Mechanical Engineering, Assiatant Professor, University of Tehran

⁴ BSc In Mechanical Engineering, After-Sales Engineer

⁵ PhD. In Mechanical Engineering, Rotor Dynamics Expert

⁶ M.Sc. In Mechanical Engineering, Head of Rotor Dynamics Department

⁷ M.Sc. In Mechanical Engineering, Deputy of Design Burea Manager

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energy of the shaft to the process gas and causes an increase in its pressure. Impeller failure is quite prevalent in centrifugal compressors due to complex dynamic loading and harsh operating conditions [1]. Required discharge pressure of centrifugal compressors increases continuously, and so do fluid densities inside the cavities, increasing the forces acting on impeller. Although the vibrational behavior of impellers has been studied extensively, the fluid-structure interactions are still to be studied thoroughly. Moreover, acoustic modes of the side cavities of centrifugal compressors were found to be another potential root cause of high cycle fatigue of impellers [2]. So coupled acoustoelastic modes need to be investigated to ensure safe and reliable operation of the equipment.

Acoustic phenomena in turbomachinery are often studied in isolation, separate from the broader fluid dynamics involved in such applications. Numerous studies have focused on these phenomena, particularly in relation to axial compressors. In their seminal work, Tyler and Sofrin [2] investigated the interactions between rotating and stationary components in axial machines, identifying rotating pressure patterns generated by rotor-stator interactions as a significant source of acoustic excitation. These patterns later became known as the Tyler/Sofrin modes. Joppa [3] subsequently observed that even when the rotating and stationary components were placed at considerable distances, Tyler/Sofrin modes could still be generated. More recent studies have explored acoustic resonances in various contexts, including low-speed multi-stage axial compressors by Camp [4], aero-engine intakes by Cooper and Peake [5] and Cooper et al. [6], and in high-speed axial compressors by Hellmich and Seume [7].

Research on acoustic phenomena in centrifugal machines is relatively limited compared to axial counterparts. Eckert [8] and Ni [9] reported fatigue in radial fan impellers caused by interactions with acoustic phenomena. Ziada et al. [10] identified that vortices shed from downstream struts in a centrifugal compressor could excite acoustic modes, leading to excessive impeller vibration. To better understand the interaction between impellers and acoustic modes in centrifugal machines, Eisinger [11] and Eisinger and Sullivan [12] proposed a simplified analytical approach. Their work highlighted the significance of complete coincidence, where coupling between a structural mode and an acoustic mode is strongest when their frequencies are closely matched, and their mode shapes are similar. This coupling can generate high stresses and cause fatigue in impellers. Additionally, Eisinger and Sullivan [13] demonstrated that modifying the shape of the acoustic spaces within the fan casing could alter the acoustic mode shapes, thereby reducing the strength of such coupling in radial fan impellers.

As recurring failure was reported for the 5th stage impeller of an eight-stage integrally geared compressor. This research was launched as an attempt to discover the root cause of failure. The failures seemed to follow the same pattern every time with masses breaking apart from the shroud's outer diameter in areas between two blades (Figure 1). This failure is believed to be related to acoustic phenomenon and its interaction with the natural frequencies of the impeller.

Figure 1- Failed 5th-stage impeller showing areas of material loss at two locations and cracks identified in four other areas.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Compressor Specifications

The equipment in question is a MAN-manufactured integrally geared compressor with eight stages, designed for handling CO₂ as the process gas. Detailed specifications of the compressor are provided in Table 1. The failed stage operates at a pressure ratio of 2 and a rotational speed of 20,021 rpm, as outlined in Table 2.

Table 1- Compressor Specifications

Parameter	Unit	Value
Compressor Type	[-]	Integrally Geared
Manufacturer	[-]	MAN Turbo
Governing Standard	[-]	API-617 (Part 1 & 3)
No. of Stages	[-]	8
Inlet Pressure – 1 st Stage	[barA]	1.55
Discharge Pressure – 8 st Stage	[barA]	157.9
Inlet Temperature – 1 st Stage	[°C]	40
Discharge Temperature – 8 st Stage	[°C]	120
Speed, 1 st & 2 nd Stages	[rpm]	8432
Speed, 3 rd & 4 th Stages	[rpm]	16381
Speed, 5 th & 6 th Stages	[rpm]	20021
Speed, 7 th & 8 th Stages	[rpm]	25741
Power	[kW]	13800
Gas Composition	[%]	99% CO ₂

Table 2- Data Related to the Failed Stage (5th Stage)

Parameter	Unit	Value
Stage No.	[-]	5 th
Inlet Pressure of the Stage	[barA]	22.59
Outlet Pressure of the Stage	[barA]	45.63
Inlet Temperature	[°C]	40
Outlet Temperature	[°C]	105
Operating Speed of the Stage	[rpm]	20,021

2.2 Impeller Modal Analysis

The first approach in identifying the root cause of a failure is typically static stress analysis. Therefore, the initial step in this research involved evaluating the safety factor of the impeller against static stresses arising from centrifugal forces and fluid pressure exerted on it. This analysis indicated high safety factors, conclusively ruling out material strength as the cause of failure. Consequently, dynamic phenomena needed to be investigated. The next logical step was to examine the modal behavior of the impeller, as it provides fundamental insights into its dynamic characteristics.

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To determine the natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes of the impeller, an eigenvalue problem must be solved. Finite Element Method (FEM) was employed for this purpose, with ANSYS Workbench 2023 selected as the computational tool. Simplifying engineering assumptions were applied to streamline the analysis while maintaining accuracy. The boundary condition was assumed to be free, and the rotational speed of the corresponding stage (gyroscopic effect) was incorporated into the impeller analysis. The impeller material was assumed to be typical steel with density, module of elasticity and Poisson ratio of $7850 \frac{kg}{m^3}$, $200 GPa$ and 0.3 , respectively.

2.3 Rotor-Stator Interaction (Tyler-Sofrin Modes)

It can be shown that rotor/stator interaction creates a plurality of spinning modes corresponding to the single frequency which is commonly referred to as Tyler/Sofrin (TS) modes. The theoretical basis of TS modes was first presented in the fundamental paper of Tyler and Sofrin [3]. Number of nodal diameters (NDs), forced TS modes (m_{TS}), is characterized by a linear combination of number of blades (Z_B), diffuser vanes (Z_{DV}), inlet guide vanes (Z_{IGV}) and return guide vanes (Z_{RGV}) which is stated as:

$$m_{TS} = ND = |h_B Z_B + h_{VD} Z_{VD} + h_{IGV} Z_{IGV} + h_{RGV} Z_{RGV}| \quad (1)$$

Where h_B , h_{VD} , h_{IGV} , and h_{RGV} are constants which range over all positive and negative integers. In order for the frequency interference to happen (TS mode shapes), the following two conditions must be met simultaneously:

- Number of nodal diameters (ND) of the resonant mode must equal the sum or difference of rotating blades (Z_B), and number of stationary vanes (Z_{VD} , Z_{IGV} , Z_{RGV}). Integer multiples of the blades and vanes also apply (equation (1)).
- The frequency of the resonant vibration must equal the same integer multiple of the stationary vane pass frequency (equations (2), (3)).

$$m_{TS}^R = |h_{VD} Z_{VD} + h_{IGV} Z_{IGV} + h_{RGV} Z_{RGV}| \quad (2)$$

$$\omega_{TS}^R = \omega_{shaft}^S m_{TS}^R \quad (3)$$

In equation (2), m_{TS}^R is the order of harmonic frequency impact, ω_{shaft}^S is the shaft speed, and ω_{TS}^R is the exciting frequency. In current case, stationary elements have no vanes ($Z_{VD} = Z_{IGV} = Z_{RGV} = 0$). Maximum nodal diameter would be simply one-half the number of blades. According to [4], modes do not exist beyond this nodal diameter limit. Certainly, for a pure disc with no blades there would be no limit to the number of nodal diameters that can exist. According to the number of blades ($Z_B=18$) and maximum possible ND of nine, there is no integer number to satisfy the equation (1). Thus Tyler-Sofrin phenomenon is not a credible explanation for the failure in this case.

2.4 Acoustic Eigen-Mode Analysis

To determine the acoustic eigenfrequencies and their corresponding eigenmodes for the fluid domain, an eigenvalue problem must be solved. The finite element method (FEM) is employed for this purpose, using ANSYS Workbench 2023 as the chosen tool. Simplifying engineering assumptions are applied to streamline the analysis, with details of these assumptions and the modeling approach provided in the following sub-sections.

2.4.1 Uniform Fluid Properties

Fluid properties such as mass density and speed of sound vary considerably through the flow domain. As stated in Table 3, mass density at the input of the stage is about $41 \frac{kg}{m^3}$ while being $70 \frac{kg}{m^3}$ at the output. However, it is quite a bit of computational burden to try to consider variable fluid properties in the acoustic modal analysis. As an attempt to tackle this issue, the assumption of uniform and constant fluid

properties in the whole flow domain was utilized in previous researches [12, 14-17]. So, the constant fluid properties thorough the flow domain are assumed in this project. For this purpose, the average values of the inlet and outlet properties are calculated and implemented to the model (Table 4).

Although the assumption of uniform and constant properties through the whole fluid domain is approved and recommended in the literature, a sensitivity analysis is done in this project to numerically justify this simplifying assumption. For this purpose, the model is implemented with the input properties and with the output properties separately. The results of two models show a maximum difference of 8 percent. These results are only 4 percent away from those of the average properties model.

Table 3- Fluid properties at inlet and outlet corresponding to different operating conditions

	Operating Condition					
	Normal		Rated		Turndown	
	Inlet	Outlet	Inlet	Outlet	Inlet	Outlet
Density (kg/m ³)	41	70	42	70	41	70
Speed of Sound (m/s)	275	301	275	302	276	302

Table 4- Fluid Properties used for the whole fluid domain

	Normal Operation
	Average
Density (kg/m ³)	56
Speed of Sound (m/s)	289

2.4.2 Fluid Domain Extent

It has been stated that the acoustic mode coupling between hub-side cavity and shroud-side cavity results in impeller failure [17]. So, the fluid domain is modeled to only contain shroud and hub side cavities (Figure 2-d). However, more detailed versions of the fluid domain are modeled to make sure that no mode shape of interest would be lost. The complete fluid domain for the 5th stage can be seen in Figure 2. This model consists of hub and shroud side cavities, diffuser and all other areas that the fluid can flow in, while the machine is in operation. All four versions are analyzed and the acoustic eigen modes and eigen frequencies are extracted. A detailed comparison of the results shows that all four models contain mode shapes resembling the shape of the failure (coin-shaped breakages on the shroud at the edges of the impeller). The fluid domain shown in Figure 2-d is used hereafter, since it needs lower number of elements and subsequently lower computational costs.

**Figure 2- Fluid domain models with different extent. a) Complete fluid domain
b) Complete fluid domain without diffuser area, c) Removed barrel shaped part, d) Fluid domain consists of only hub and shroud side cavities**

2.4.3 Stationary Impeller and Stagnant Fluid

The most restrictive assumptions are stationary impeller and stagnant fluid. In reality the flow field in the side cavities is highly complex and unsteady. For such a case the fluid dynamics and acoustics of the system are fully coupled and no eigen value problem can be posed [17]. If not calling such an analysis impossible in this stage, it is definitely too complicated to be solved in an industrial project like this. Fortunately, Konig [17] has validated this assumption by experiment. However, there have been some attempts to eliminate these restricting assumptions recently [18], but it will not be in the scope of this project.

2.4.4 Acoustic Boundary Conditions

One important aspect of engineering simulations is the implementation of suitable boundary conditions (BCs) that are well aligned with the reality of the phenomena. Although being strictly valid only for plane waves, characteristic impedance boundary conditions, representing non-reflecting BCs, are applied to the inlet and outlet of the computational domain [17].

3 Results

This section presents the findings of the impeller modal analysis and acoustic eigen-mode analysis. The results are illustrated through two sets of graphs, providing insights into the dynamic characteristics of the impeller and acoustic characteristics of the fluid domain.

3.1 Modal Analysis Results

The results of structural modal analysis are presented in Figure 3. In this figure the mode shapes, which are related to Nodal Diameters¹ (ND=2 to ND=9), are illustrated. As it is seen in the operating speed (20464 rpm), due to the gyroscopic effect, forward and backward modes are far enough away from each other, and this issue is even more severe in higher modes.

Figure 3- Structural Modal Analysis of the Impeller, only the main mode shapes ND=2 to 9 are reported. Each picture is representative of two similar mode shapes (forward, backward modes) except for the last one that is a single mode

¹ Stationary lines on a vibrating structure that divide it into segments vibrating out of phase.

3.2 Acoustic Analysis Results

The results related to the fluid domain assumption are presented in Figure 4 and Figure 5 for ND=9 and ND=5, respectively. According to these figures, it can be seen the simplified fluid domain has not changed the acoustic eigen modes which are related to the side cavities.

Figure 4- Same Acoustic Eigen Modes for two different fluid domain models, ND=9.
a) Fluid domain just includes the side cavities, ND=9, $f=4256\text{Hz}$.
b) Complete flow domain model, ND=9, $f=4260\text{Hz}$.

Figure 5- Same Acoustic Eigen Modes for two different fluid domain models, ND=5.
a) Fluid domain just includes the side cavities, ND=5, $f=2343\text{Hz}$.
b) Complete flow domain model, ND=5, $f=2433\text{Hz}$.

4 Discussion

Results of the impeller modal analysis and acoustic eigen-mode analysis revealed specific mode shapes, whose interaction is believed to be the root cause of the impeller failure. The observed failure patterns show a strong correlation with these mode shapes, further supporting this hypothesis. This section delves deeper into these findings, contextualizing them within the framework of existing research and engineering practices to provide a comprehensive understanding of the failure mechanism and propose potential preventive measures.

4.1 Potential Underlying Causes of Failure

Following the modal analysis results, it is crucial to investigate potential interactions between the acoustic and structural modes that could have contributed to the impeller failure. As shown in Figure 7, the structural modes generally occur at frequencies well above those of the acoustic modes, except for one with a nodal diameter (ND) of nine. The fracture pattern observed on the impeller also closely

resembles the structural mode shape with ND=9 (see Figure 6), raising the suspicion that mode(s) with ND=9 may be linked to recurring fractures.

Figure 6- a) Hypothetical failure mode shape based on the pattern of breakages, ND=9
b) A similar structural mode shape to the hypothetical failure mode, ND=9

Figure 7- a) Frequency Vs. Nodal Diameter for structural and acoustic eigen frequencies. b) Zoomed area of probable interference between acoustic and structural modes.

As the structural modes characterized by ND=9 are suspicious to be the failure mode shapes, the acoustic modes characterized by ND=9 should be investigated to check if they are capable of exciting above-mentioned structural modes. According to the literature [19], the necessary condition for being certain about the existence of an interference between structural and acoustic modes is the same number of

NDs. However, the sufficient condition to be sure of no interaction between acoustics and structure is a separation margin of at least 25% between the eigen frequencies of structural and acoustic modes. Although the necessary condition for the elasto-acoustic interactions is described to be the same NDs and no further information is given about the possibility of interaction between modes with the same number of nodal circles (NCs), in our case there is an acoustic eigen mode characterized by ND=0, NC=1 (Figure 8-b) and corresponding eigen frequency of 5176Hz. On the other hand, there is a structural eigen mode characterized by ND=0, NC=1 and eigen frequency of 5347Hz which is an axially-dominant deformed mode shape (Figure 8-a). This extreme axial deformation seems to cause the edges of the shroud to be harshly loaded and deformed between any two blades, causing 9 highly loaded areas to appear on the edges of the shroud which resembles an ND of nine. So, one probable candidate for the failure would be the interaction and coupling between these two modes.

Figure 8- Potential interaction between acoustic and structural eigen modes with NC=1.
a) Axial structural mode with edges of the shroud being highly deformed, NC=1, $f=5347$ Hz.
b) An acoustic eigen mode that can excite the impeller in axial direction, NC=1, $f=5176$ Hz.

Another acoustic eigen mode that can be capable of exciting the structural eigen mode of NC=1 is shown in Figure 9 which is characterized by ND=9 and eigen frequency of 4264Hz. These two modes have a minimum frequency separation margin of 20%. It is also noteworthy that there is a pair of acoustic and structural eigen modes with ND=1 and very close eigen frequencies (safety margin of 11%) which are presented in Figure 10. Furthermore, Figure 11 represents a more informative look of the possible interactions between elastic and acoustic modes.

Figure 9- Potential interaction between acoustic and structural eigen modes with ND=9.
a) Axial structural mode with edges of the shroud being highly deformed, NC=1, $f=5347$ Hz.
b) Acoustic eigen mode that can excite the edges of the shroud, ND=9, $f=4264$ Hz.

Figure 10- Potential interaction between acoustic and structural eigen modes with ND=1.
a) Structural eigen mode with ND=1, f=598 Hz. b) Acoustic eigen mode with ND=1, f=532 Hz

Figure 11- Elastic and acoustic modes capable of interacting with each other.

4.2 Viable Redesign Solutions

As it is shown in Figure 7, the natural frequencies of the impeller are well away from the acoustic eigen frequencies except for some modes with ND=9. These modes are discussed in more detail in previous section and they are suspected to be the root cause of the failure. So, the easiest solution for this problem is to reduce the probability of interference between structural and acoustic modes in the mentioned area by increasing the distance between them. This can be achieved by increasing the natural frequencies of the impeller. For this purpose, either the equivalent stiffness of the impeller should be increased or its equivalent mass should be reduced. Increasing the stiffness is not feasible, since it is mostly governed by the inherent properties of the material. But reducing equivalent mass is more of a practical option. For example, Grebinyk et al. [20] from SULZER used scalloping to modify an impeller which had broken previously due to impeller diffuser interactions (Figure 12). Moreover, changing the profile of the shroud surface can be done in a way that results in an increase in the impeller natural frequencies. There can be numerous alternative methods to modify the design, but their undesirable side effects should be investigated to ensure safe and reliable operation of the equipment.

Figure 12- a) Broken shroud due to impeller-diffuser interactions.
b) Modified impeller design by scalloping [20]

4.2.1 Scalloping

The impeller model is scalloped with two different patterns and the structural modal analysis is repeated. The first scallop has a simple profile, Figure 13-a, while the second one follows a more complex curve which is adopted from the mode shape of concern, Figure 13-c.

Figure 13- a) Redesigned impeller by scalloping with simple pattern. b) The suspected mode of failure (mode of concern). c) Redesigned impeller by scalloping with a special pattern adopted from the mode of concern.

4.2.2 Modification of Shroud Thickness Profile

Radgolchin et al. [21] have investigated the effect of blade and shroud thickness profiles on the aeromechanical and fatigue life of impellers. They concluded that there is an optimal value for the shroud thickness that corresponds to the minimum equivalent stress and maximum fatigue life. In addition to their research on evaluation of equivalent stress values, the effect of the shroud thickness profile on the acoustoelastic behavior of the impeller should be investigated.

Adding mass to the edges of the impeller is definitely a bad idea since it decreases the structural natural frequencies of the impeller resulting in a reduction of margin between acoustic and structural modes. However, adding mass to the impeller somewhere away from the edges may contradict the previous scenario. This behavior can be enhanced by trying more complex shroud profiles.

Figure 14 shows the results for two types of scalloped models, (4) and (5). Furthermore, it also represents the mode of concern for the original MAN design, (3), the design with added ring at the edge of impeller, (1), and the design with added ring away from the edge of impeller, (2). The scalloped designs by far outperform other designs in increasing the natural frequency of concern. This figure also indicates that the addition of a ring on the edge of impeller has exacerbated the interference between acoustic and

structural mode causing the impeller to fail in a shorter period of time relative to the original design of MAN.

Figure 14- - The effect of different designs on increasing the margin between acoustic and structural modes. (1) added ring at the impeller edge. (2) added ring away from edges. (3) original MAN design. (4) simple pattern scallop. (5) more complex-pattern scallop.

4.2.3 Other Modification Methods

Some other improvement methods have been identified, which will be investigated in future works. Some of these suggestions are as follow:

- Adding splitters between blades
- Impeller redesign with 17 blades (present designs have 18 blades)
- A combination of previously mentioned methods

5 Conclusion

Repetitive failure of the 5th stage impeller of the CO₂ compressor owned by Shiraz PC company has occurred through the last 5 years. Reportedly, all failures have shown the same fracture shapes and patterns. As it was investigated through this research, we are almost certain that the failure cannot be justified by conventional methods of strengths of materials and the root cause of the failure should be looked for in the fluid-structure interactions. For this purpose, the impeller-diffuser interactions known as Tyler-Sofrin modes were suspected. However, it cannot be the case since neither the diffuser nor the inlet of the stage are vaned. Another phenomenon introduced in the literature as the root cause of the failure of impellers in high pressure centrifugal compressors, is the acousto-elastic interactions. The acoustic eigen modes for the fluid domain are obtained from an acoustic modal analysis using ANSYS Workbench 2023. Furthermore, the structural natural frequencies are calculated by conducting a modal analysis. Afterwards, both the structural modes and acoustic modes are plotted in a single diagram to recognize any probable interference between acoustic modes and structural ones. The structural modes are well away from the acoustic modes. However, there are two structural modes characterized by ND=9 which have a similar pattern to the real fracture shape and pattern. There are corresponding acoustic modes which can be coupled with these structural modes. This potential coupling between structural and acoustic modes is introduced as the probable root cause of the failure.

The acoustic eigenmodes are largely determined by the fluid path geometry and properties and cannot be significantly altered. Therefore, modifying the structural eigenmodes of the impeller has been identified as a primary approach for improvement. Adjusting the structural eigenvalues can be achieved by altering the impeller's design, such as through scalloping and adjusting the thickness profile of the shroud. Additional improvement methods will be explored in the next phase of the project.

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